

**POPULATION STRUCTURE OF KUSAVALI VILLAGE, IN MAWAL TAHSIL IN PUNE
DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA, INDIA**

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Abstract:

Population structure is important role for rural development. in rural area less development of industry, transport facility and other activity. Due to most of the occupation is in primary like Agriculture, Animal rearing, mining and others. This paper represent population structure with help of dependency ratio, age sex pyramid, child women ratio, literacy rate and how impact on rural development.

The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data including the field survey, secondary data from grampanchayat of kusavali village, computer based technique and Toposheet. This paper is focus on the economic assessments of rural with help of following parameters these are population structure with educational status of rural population in major centers of grampanchayat of kusavali village.

Key Words: - *Field Survey, Spatial Analysis, Maps, graphs, Tables and Various statistical techniques.*

1. Introduction:

The village is very small unit of human settlement. The village is also one of the good examples of stage of cultural development of man on the surface of the earth. Geographer's role is to understand this stage of cultural development and its relationship with natural environment.

The survey provides the primary data regarding different aspects of life style of man in the village. Environment has direct impact on village culture. Natural phenomenon directly governs the village setup. Therefore it is very important to study natural phenomenon along with human beings. The government of India and government of Maharashtra continuously try to develop the villages, as the 3/4th of the Indian population lives in this habitat. Government introduces many schemes for people's welfare. Urban people have least contact with villagers therefore it is necessary to visit the village to see the percolation extent of government plans and schemes to find out the problem and finally to conclude the suggestion.

2. Objective:

To find out the population structure in Kusavali Village.

3. Methodology:

The primary data and secondary data have been used for the research paper. The questionnaire has been prepared to collect the data. The statistical method has been used for data calculation.

3.1 Data collection:

Data collection has done with the help of the observation, interviews, photos, Google images and field survey. Questionnaires have prepared for obtaining information of solid waste& tin-bin system. However spatial analysis of study area has been done on Google image using Arc GIS in to calculate area and related features. This paper shows

Topographical map is very important tool for geographers. Give the Toposheet no 47 F/8 with the help of this Toposheet we got the information about Location of study area, Relief of study area & surrounding area, Drainage around the study area, Different natural and cultural aspects of village.

4. The location of study area:

The Village Kusavali is located between $18^{\circ} 52'41''$ N latitudes and $73^{\circ}30'80''$ E longitudes at 658m mean sea level in the taluka of Maval, district of Pune, in the State of Maharashtra. It is located 54 KM towards west from District head quarters Pune and 85 KM from State capital Mumbai. Kusavali Pin code is 412106 and postal head office is Vadgaon (Pune). Village Vahangaon is situated in north of Kusavali, in the eastern side Nagathali village is situated, village Vadeshwar is situated in south-western side and in the south of Kusavali Shradhe village is situated. Marathi is the Local Language here.

Fig No1: Location of Study Area

Soure: GPS Surveyed by Researcher

5. Population Structure:

Population structure is typically presented in a pyramid-style format. Population pyramids can be large or small, depending on the size of population they represent and the different factors that they display.

Population pyramids show the breakdown of populations in towns, cities, continents or countries based on certain characteristics, such as gender, socioeconomic status and age. These pyramids organize population data and are useful for showing trends and patterns of the past, present and future.

5.1 Gender wise Population:

Physical as well as cultural settings are also a major factor in the study of any region. In cultural setting population aspects plays an important role in determining the cultural setup of the particular region. If the number of people is more it will increase the working capacity of the population if it is excessively more it

could be a burden on the village environment. Demographic aspects are very important when we deal with population. Population determines the basic strength for the village improvement. If the number of people is more it will increase the working capacity of the population. But it would be a burden if the population were excessive than the capacity. In the village like Kusavali population is more.

There are some basic characteristics which are important to understand the socio-economic condition of village. The characteristics include demographic factors like fertility, morality and migration.

Table No. 1: Gender wise total Population

Gender	Population	Percentage
Male	203	54.86
Female	167	45.14
Total	370	100

Fig. No. 2: Gender wise total Population

The total population of Kusavali village is 370 and Male Population is 203 (54.86%) and Female is 167 (45.14). Here Male population is greater than Female population.

5.2 Age-Sex Pyramid:

Age sex data determines the age composition in different age group of particular region. It indicates the stage of development that whether the region is developed/under developed / developing it is easy to understand the working capacity of population & its burden on the present sources. The graph shows that (less than 15 years and more than 60 years) dependent population is maximum indicate domino of working population.

Table No.2: Age-sex Pyramid

Age Group	Male	Male (%)	Female	Female (%)
0-4	18	8.82	8	4.79
5-9	17	8.33	10	5.99
10-14	12	5.88	18	10.78
15-19	13	6.37	20	11.98
20-24	25	12.25	20	11.98
25-29	23	11.27	18	10.78
30-34	20	9.80	15	8.98
35-39	19	9.31	13	7.78

40-44	13	6.37	05	2.99
45-49	08	3.92	13	7.78
50-54	13	6.37	03	1.80
55-59	03	1.47	8	4.79
60-64	08	3.92	7	4.19
65-69	5	2.45	5	2.99
70-74	5	2.45	4	2.40
75-79	2	0.98	-	-
Total	204	100	167	100

Fig. No. 3: Age-sex Fig. No. 3: Age-sex Pyramid

This is a broad pyramid with wide middle. This indicates the adult population is high or compare to the young population. It has narrow top which indicates low proportion of old people. It can be said that it is a case optimum population. Thus this village is a condition of developing situation.

5.3 Dependency Ratio:

The age composition can be studied with the help of age indices. The calculation of age indices is significant purpose of man power planning growth of population analysis etc. “The ratio between adult on one hand and children and aged on the other hand is known as dependency ratio” Dependency Male & Female ratio of Kusavali village has 41.38 & 32.54 respectively. It has Less than 200. It indicates the region is in developing stage.

Table No. 3: Dependency Ratio

Gender	0-14	15-64	Above- 65
Male	48	145	12
Female	36	126	05
Total	84	271	17

Fig. No. 4: Dependency Ratio

5.4 Child Woman Ratio:

It is the ratio between number of children of age group below 5 years and no of women age group 15 to 45 years. The Child Woman Ratio for the study area is 250. It is greater than 200. It shows child woman ratio has high.

Table No.4: Child Women Ratio

Age Group	Population
0-4	26
15-49	104

Fig. No.5: Child Women Ratio

5.5. Literacy Rate:

Due to the availability of school and trained staff children have taken interest in studies and ever the elders of the family have recognized the importance of education. Male literacy rate is higher than female literacy rate in year 2015. Literacy is the indicator of education awareness of any rural area. Literate and illiterate ratio shows the education background of the village Kusavali. Literate and illiterate population distribution clearly shows there is increasing trend in the literate population. Total literacy of the male is 56.59% and women 43.41% in 2015.

The data relating to literacy were collected by questionnaires. The data is shown in the following table.

Table No.5: Literacy Rate

Gender	Literacy	Percentage (%)
Male	103	56.59
Female	79	43.41
Total	182	100

Fig. No.6: Literacy Rate

6. Conclusion:

The aims & objectives stated for this study which has been supportively elaborated and interpreted by the many findings and conclusion driven the various ways of this study. The conclusions were elaborated in the following ways.

Total population in Kusavli is very different Male and Female sex ratio. Here Male population is greater than Female population. This is a broad pyramid with wide middle. This indicates the adult population is high or compare to the young population. It has narrow top which indicates low proportion of old people. It can be said that it is a case optimum population. Thus this village is a condition of developing situation. Male & Female ratio of Kusavli village has 41.38 & 32.54 respectively. It has Less than 200. It indicates the region is in developing stage. Child Woman Ratio for the study area is 250. It is greater than 200. It shows child woman ratio has high. The Kusavli Village Literate and illiterate population distribution clearly shows there is increasing trend in the literate population. Total literacy of the male is 56.59% and women 43.41% in 2015.

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